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SOME THOUGHTS ON UZBEKISTAN'S AGRICULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS AND THE SILK ROAD GRAIN CORRIDOR

Citation Xu Haiyan

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Xu Haiyan ^{1*}

¹ The Center for Russian and Central Asian Studies, Institute of
International Studies, Fudan University, China

*Corresponding author: haiyanxu_708@fudan.edu.cn

Abstract. Uzbekistan, being the largest agricultural country in the Aral Sea Basin, has a significant portion of arable land and is a key player in cotton production, fruit and vegetable cultivation, and silkworm breeding. The country's agriculture is concentrated in oasis areas such as the Fergana Valley and is heavily reliant on irrigation due to its dry climate. Uzbekistan's agriculture contributes significantly to its economy, with cotton being a major export commodity. We also highlights the historical context of agricultural development in the region, the ecological challenges posed by extensive irrigation, and the country's efforts to adopt water-saving technologies and invest in high-value agricultural chains. Looking forward, Uzbekistan aims to expand its cultivation area, increase crop yields, and enhance its position as a "vegetable basket" on the Silk Road Economic Belt..

Keywords: Uzbekistan agriculture, Aral Sea Basin, cotton production, water-saving technologies, Silk Road Economic Belt.

1 INTRODUCTION

The land in the Aral Sea Basin can be divided into two parts: the Turan Plain and the mountainous area. The western and northwestern parts of the Aral Sea Basin belong to the Turan Plain, which is partially covered by the Karakum and Kyzylkum Deserts. Agriculture is concentrated in the "oasis" areas of the Fergana Valley, Khorezm, Dashaouz, Mana, Zeravshan, Tashkent-Shymkent, etc. The "oasis" covers a small area, but due to the suitable conditions for farming (water, rainfall, fertile soil, etc.), it has been the center of human activities and residence in this area since ancient times.

1.1. Uzbekistan is the largest agricultural country in the Aral Sea basin

Of the 59.16 million hectares of arable land in the Aral Sea Basin, Uzbekistan has 25.45 million hectares, accounting for 43.01% of the Aral Sea Basin. Among the five countries in the Aral Sea Basin, it occupies the most arable land in the basin, followed by Kazakhstan with 40.35% and Turkmenistan with 11.85%. Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan account for 2.66% and 2.13% respectively;

of the 59.16 million hectares of arable land, only about 10 million hectares have been cultivated, of which Uzbekistan occupies 5.21 million hectares, accounting for 52.08%, far ahead of other Central Asian Aral Sea countries. Although Kazakhstan occupies 40.35% of the arable land in the Aral Sea Basin, its actual reclamation rate is 16.95%, Turkmenistan accounts for 18.05%, Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan account for 7.7% and 5.9% respectively. From the above, Uzbekistan is indeed the largest agricultural country in the Aral Sea basin.

Table 1. Land ownership in the Aral Sea Basin of the five Central Asian countries (unit: hectare)

Countries	Area	Arable land	Cultivated land	Irrigation area
Kazakhstan	34440000	23872400	1658800	786200
Kyrgyzstan	1249000	1257400	595000	422000
Tajikistan	1431000	1571000	769900	719000
Turkmenistan	48810000	7013000	1805300	173500
Uzbekistan	44884000	25447700	5207800	4233400
Aral Sea Basin	154934000	59161500	10036800	7895600

Uzbekistan is located in the Aral Sea-Syr Darya, Amu Darya and Chu River basins. The Aral Sea Basin includes the entire territories of Uzbekistan and Tajikistan, most of Turkmenistan, the three provinces of Osh, Jalal-Abad and Naryn in Kyrgyzstan, Kyzylorda and South Kazakhstan in Kazakhstan, as well as the northern part of Afghanistan and Iran. Here only the first five countries are involved, with a total area of 1.549 million square kilometers. According to the Aral Sea database, there are 59 million hectares of arable land, 10 million hectares of which have been cultivated, and there are 49 million hectares of potential land to be cultivated, of which about 24.7 million hectares are easily irrigated arable land, and about 24.3 million hectares are hillside land that is difficult to irrigate

It has an agricultural population of 18 million, accounting for about 50% of the country's total population. It has 25.45 million hectares of arable land and 5.21 million hectares of cultivated land, with an average per capita arable land area of about 0.71 hectares, higher than the world's average level. In the 1950s, the Soviet Union selected the Ishim River Basin in northern Kazakhstan and the Syr Darya and Amu Darya River Basins of the Aral Sea as its main reclamation areas in Central Asia during the large-scale reclamation movement. Because the Amu Darya and Syr Darya were once the source rivers of Central Asian civilization, especially the Amu Darya delta, which gave birth to the brilliant "Khwarazm" civilization about 3,000 years ago, from the perspective of historical geography, the academic community sometimes calls it the "Two Rivers Basin in Central Asia". In order to avoid confusion with the well-known "Two Rivers Basin" of the Tigris and Euphrates in Western Asia, the word "Central Asia" is added in front. "Khwarazm" was once the source of regional civilization in Central Asia, and there was a 10-year archaeological excavation in the Soviet era.

This has made these two regions the main reclamation areas in Central Asia to this day. The former is mainly planted with wheat and has become one of the important granaries of the Soviet Union; the latter is mainly planted with cotton. During this period, Uzbekistan's agriculture has

developed rapidly and has become an important cotton base (known as the "Platinum Plan") and vegetable, fruit base of the Soviet Union. Agriculture is an important part of Uzbekistan's economy. The output value of agriculture accounts for about one-third of its GDP, the output value of cotton accounts for 40% of agriculture, and the export of agricultural products accounts for 8.4% of Uzbekistan's external income. Therefore, after its independence, Uzbekistan paid great attention to agricultural development and agricultural reform.

1.2. The outstanding highlights of uzbekistan's agriculture are cotton, fruit and vegetable cultivation and silkworm breeding

Except for the southeastern part which is mountainous, most of Uzbekistan's land is grassland, desert, Gobi, and the central and western parts are the Kyzyl Kum Desert, with plains and basins in between. The Turan Plain, Fergana Basin and Amu Darya Delta are its key agricultural areas, where there is abundant sunshine, long light hours for plants, and a large temperature difference between day and night, which is very suitable for the growth of cotton, fruit and vegetable. Therefore, cotton and fruit and vegetable planting have become the characteristic agriculture of Uzbekistan, and the Amu Darya and Syr Darya rivers are its irrigation water sources. The Amu Darya River, with a total length of 1,415 kilometers and an average flow of 1,330 cubic meters per second, is the largest inland river in Central Asia. It originates from the alpine glaciers at an altitude of more than 4,500 meters in the southeastern part of the Pamir Plateau. The Wakhkil River in Afghanistan is its source river. After flowing westward and merging with the Pamir River, it is called the Wakhan River and becomes the border river between Afghanistan and Tajikistan. After flowing westward to Iskasim, it is renamed the Panj River. It continues to flow westward and merges with the Vakhsh River in Tajikistan and is renamed the Amu Darya River. It flows westward and becomes the boundary river between Afghanistan and Turkmenistan. It enters Turkmenistan from Mukre and flows between the Kyzyl Kum Desert and the Karakum Desert. It is the boundary river between Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan from Dayakhatten to Gazi Achak. After that, it enters Uzbekistan and flows into the Aral Sea at Muynak. The total area of the Amu Darya River basin is 465,000 square kilometers. Below Nukus, the river is divided into several tributaries and flows into the Aral Sea, forming a fan-shaped estuary delta with an area of 10,000 square kilometers

These crops consume a lot of water. To smoothly implement the "Platinum Plan", the Soviet Union carried out large-scale water conservancy projects in the Amu Darya River Basin in the late 1950s and early 1960s. The Karakum Canal was built in 1956, the Amu Darya-Bukhara Canal was built in 1962, and the Karshi Canal was built in 1974. At the same time, a series of seasonal regulating reservoirs and regulating canals were built on some tributaries of the Amu Darya River. These canals have been taking more and more water from the Amu Darya River year by year. In the early 1950s, the water taken was about 61% of the total water volume, and in the early 1970s, it reached 68% of the total volume. At the same time, the proportion of the Amu Darya River in the total runoff interception has also changed: in the early 1950s, 83% of the water was concentrated in the lower reaches of the river; in the early 1970s, the proportion of water taken in the lower reaches dropped to about 55%, while the proportion of water taken in the middle and upper reaches increased from 13% and 4% to 16% and 29% respectively.

The irrigated land area in Uzbekistan has reached more than 4.23 million hectares. Uzbekistan has a dry climate, and irrigation agriculture is the main form of agriculture in the country. Without irrigation, there would be no agriculture in Uzbekistan. However, due to the extensive irrigation

model, water resources are seriously wasted, and serious ecological problems such as saline-alkaline lands have been caused [1].

Cotton is the main industry of Uzbekistan's agriculture. Uzbekistan is the most important cotton production base in the Soviet Union. It mainly produces medium-staple and long-staple cotton. Its cotton production once accounted for 70% of the total in the Soviet Union. In the 1980s, the production of seed cotton reached more than 6 million tons. To date, Uzbekistan is still the largest cotton producer and exporter in Central Asia. At present, the annual production of seed cotton is about 4 million tons, ranking third in the world; the production of processed lint cotton is nearly 1.1 million tons, ranking fifth in the world; the export value of lint cotton ranks second in the world, second only to the United States. Uzbek domestic textile enterprises can only "digest" about 15% of lint cotton, and the rest is exported abroad. Among the export products, cotton accounts for about 40%, which is the main source of foreign exchange for Uzbekistan. It is mainly exported to Switzerland, the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and South Korea. According to FAO statistics, in recent years, the average annual export volume of Uzbekistan's cotton is about 1 million tons, and the export value has reached 1.6 to 1.8 billion US dollars. In addition to exporting cotton, Uzbekistan also exports large quantities of raw silk, fruits, dried fruits and vegetables, and the export value of raisins can reach 14 million US dollars per year [1].

The silk industry is another highlight of Uzbekistan's agriculture. In the 3rd century AD, Chinese silkworm breeding and silk production technology were introduced to Uzbekistan through Khotan, where they took root and continued for 1700 years. Today, Uzbekistan, known as the "Mulberry Country", has 44,000 hectares of mulberry gardens and nearly 300 million scattered mulberry trees. During the Soviet period, Uzbekistan had about 50 collective farms and state farms engaged in raw silkworm production with 10 silk reeling mills. The Margilan Silk Joint Enterprise was the largest of them, followed by the Fergana Silk Reeling Mill and the Samarkand Silk Reeling Mill. The annual production capacity of the Samarkand Silk Reeling Mill alone is 236 tons. Uzbekistan's raw silk production once accounted for more than 50% of the Soviet Union. In the 1980s and early 1990s, Uzbekistan's silk cocoon production reached more than 30,000 tons. After that it declined, but in recent years it has returned to the highest level of previous years. At present, there are nearly 40 countries and regions in the world with silk production, but there are only five countries that have a certain position in this industry. Uzbekistan ranks third, after China and India, and before Brazil and Thailand [2].

Fruit and vegetable production has grown fast. Uzbekistan is an important vegetable production base in Central Asia. Its main vegetable products are tomatoes, cucumbers, onions, carrots, edible beets, eggplants, peppers, etc. The annual output of tomatoes is about 1 million tons. Grapes and fruits are abundant in the Fergana Basin, the Zeravshan Oasis, and the Amu Darya and Syr Darya River basins. The sugar content of grapes is 18% -27%, which is very popular in foreign markets.

Table 2. Changes in fruit and vegetable production in Uzbekistan from 2000 to 2023 (thousand tons)

Year	Potatoes	Vegetables	Melons	Berries	Grapes	Cereals	Silkworm cocoons
2000	731.1	2644.7	451.40	790.9	624.20	4,101.40	16.48
2001	744.4	2777.8	466.10	801.3	573.10	4240.1	17.338
2002	777.2	2935.6	479.10	842.9	516.40	5,792.50	19.93

2003	834.4	3301.4	587.30	765.8	401.50	6319.2	16.686
2004	895.7	3336.1	572.50	851.7	589.10	6,008.80	16.86
2005	924.2	3517.5	615.30	949.3	641.60	6540.9	16.211
2006	1021.0	4294.1	744.1	1182.2	803.6	6,655.10	20.25
2007	1188.9	4691.9	840.9	1270	878.9	6771	21.47
2008	1398.7	5221.3	981.3	1402.7	792.5	6735.1	23.45
2009	1530.9	5698.2	1071.3	1521	900.5	7394.8	23.97
2010	1694.8	6262.4	1182.4	1676.3	979.3	7504.3	25.15
2011	1855.1	6828.8	1294.8	1820.6	1072.1	7140.7	24.67
2012	2036.3	7459.1	1418.4	1981.7	1179.9	7519.5	25.01
2013	2216.5	8087.9	1558.3	2143.9	1294	7807.8	25.45
2014	2399.2	8753.9	1696.1	2306.5	1397	8050.5	26.1
2015	2586.8	9390	1853.6	2467.9	1518.2	8173.5	26.29
2016	2789.5	10184	2044.9	2612.9	1613.1	8261.3	26.36
2017	2793.7	10219.9	2031	2614.9	1625.5	7288.5	12.48
2018	2911.90	9760.3	1837	2706.2	1589.8	6535.5	17.91
2019	3089.70	10215.1	2068.7	2752.7	1603.3	7437.8	21.37
2020	3143.80	10431.4	2134.4	2812.6	1606.9	7636.0	20.94
2021	3285.60	10850.2	2285.3	2852.6	1695.3	7634.6	22.77
2022	3443.20	11162.9	2420.7	2999.3	1760.6	7990.5	24.30
2023	3574.10	11553.7	2553.5	3121.7	1737.6	8426.6	25.89

Figure 1. Production of fruits, vegetables and cereals in Uzbekistan from 2000 to 2023

In addition, animal husbandry is also an important industry in Uzbekistan. It has 26.5 million hectares of desert pastures. In 1998, there were 5.3 million cattle and 8 million sheep in the country. Livestock products are mainly fur and meat. The annual output of various meats is 529,000 tons and milk is 3.459 million tons. The lamb skins produced are world-famous. The annual purchase volume of high-quality Karakul lamb skins is 1.5 million pieces. In addition, 18,000 tons of coarse wool are also produced [3].

3 UZBEKISTAN IS AN IMPORTANT “VEGETABLE BASKET” ON THE SILK ROAD ECONOMIC BELT

In 2022, Uzbekistan's export of fruits and vegetables reached 1.74 million tons, mainly sold to Kazakhstan, the Russian Federation, Kyrgyzstan, China, Pakistan, Afghanistan, Belarus, Tajikistan, Turkey, Iran, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan, the United Arab Emirates and other Silk Road countries, with an export value of 1.6964 million tons, accounting for 97.29%. Here we can see that in addition to being an important energy supply base on the Silk Road Economic Belt, Uzbekistan is also an important “vegetable basket” on the Silk Road Economic Belt.

Table 3

Geographical distribution of Uzbekistan’s fruit and vegetable exports in 2022

Countries	Quantity (thousand tons)	Value (millions of dollars)	Proportion
Russian Federation	541.9	486	0.4245
Kazakhstan	641.2	216	0.1887
China	127.2	104.6	0.0914
Pakistan	65.3	101.2	0.0884
Kyrgyzstan	155.6	42.9	0.0375
Afghanistan	48.6	31.1	0.0272
Turkey	19	25.5	0.0223
Belarus	24.3	19.9	0.0174
Azerbaijan	10	14.1	0.0123
Iran	12.8	13.2	0.0115
UAE	6.8	9	0.0079
Georgia	11.7	8.4	0.0073
Tajikistan	24	7.8	0.0068
Germany	3.3	7.3	0.0064
Turkmenistan	8	7.1	0.0062
Other countries	43.9	50.7	0.0443
Total	1743.6		

*Data source: Uzbekistan Statistics Bureau

Uzbekistan has 25,447,700 hectares of arable land, of which 5,207,800 hectares are actually cultivated, and there is huge potential for expanding cultivation. The key lies in solving the problem of water sources for agricultural use. As we all know, the large-scale desert reclamation in the Soviet Union in the 1950s and 1960s created a bumper harvest in the Aral Sea basin but also

accelerated the shrinkage of the Aral Sea. The Karakum Canal intercepts one-third of the Amu Darya water flowing into the Aral Sea (503 m/s). In the 1960s, a large number of immigrants came to the Karakum Canal basin and reclaimed and irrigated 6.6 million hectares of cotton and rice fields, resulting in a bumper cotton harvest and high rice yield. The annual output of crops increased by 4 times compared with the previous period, providing the Soviet Union with 95% of cotton and 40% of rice and many vegetables, fruits and melons, making the Soviet Union a major cotton exporter. The harvest of agricultural production and economic development promoted regional immigration, and the population soared from 7 million to more than 36 million. However, behind this success lies an ecological crisis: the expansion of irrigated land has led to the shrinkage of the Aral Sea.

Agriculture consumes 90% of Uzbekistan's water resources. Uzbekistan is taking strong measures to subsidize the use of agricultural water-saving technologies and spend \$826 million on the construction of 299 modern pumping stations between 2021 and 2026, aiming to save at least 7 billion cubic meters of water by 2026. These measures will help expand the cultivated area and increase crop yields. The Uzbek government plans to invest US\$1 billion in projects to create high-value agricultural chains, with the goal of expanding fruit and vegetable production, increasing fruit and vegetable processing capacity to 3.2 million tons, milk production to 3 million tons, and meat processing to 450,000 tons. It also plans to double textile production by 2026.¹ It is expected that more Uzbek agricultural products will be run on the Silk Road food corridor in the future.

These canals have been taking more and more water from the Amu Darya River year by year. In the early 1950s, the water taken was about 61% of the total water volume, and in the early 1970s, it reached 68% of the total volume. At the same time, the proportion of the Amu Darya River in the total runoff interception has also changed: in the early 1950s, 83% of the water was concentrated in the lower reaches of the river; in the early 1970s, the proportion of water taken in the lower reaches dropped to about 55%, while the proportion of water taken in the middle and upper reaches increased from 13% and 4% to 16% and 29% respectively.

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¹ According to the World Bank, Uzbekistan ranks 20th from the bottom in the world in terms of water productivity, producing just \$0.6 per cubic meter of water, compared to a global average of \$15 per cubic meter.

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